

Satisfaction Level of Students and Faculty in the Usage of N-List of Various Degree Colleges Affiliated to Punjab University Chandigarh

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ABSTRACT

This research paper explains the usage of the N-LIST e-resources among the students and faculty members of the various selected degree colleges affiliated to Panjab University, Chandigarh. A questionnaire method was used as a tool for collection of data from the 32 selected degree colleges in Punjab and Chandigarh. The total data was collected from 466 out of 513 respondents. The total response rate is 90.84%. Out of 466 respondents, total 286 are users and 180 are non-users (faculty and student) respondents. The statistical test has been applied and the inferences have been drawn thereof for identifying the satisfaction level of the faculty and student respondents in library support and ICT infrastructural facilities by the select degree colleges of Panjab University, Chandigarh. This study helps in identifying the strengths and weakness of the consortium in evaluating the performance of N-LIST e-resources. It will also throw a flood of light on the measures needed to be undertaken to make the N-LIST consortium more effective and successful.

KeyTerms: e-Books, e-Journals, Bibliographical Databases, N-LIST, Academic Pursuits, Learning Outcomes

INTRODUCTION

With the advent of resource sharing, the library consortia have brought economy, efficiency and equality in information availability and its usage. Through library consortia, the gap between information resource-rich libraries and resource-deficient libraries is expected to be bridged. Although, there are many consortia in India like UGC-INFONET Digital Library Consortia, INDEST Consortia, CSIR Consortia etc. which have already gained the popularity in India. Yet, N-LIST is one of such consortia which helps to bridge this gap and provides access to the e-resources to its users.

N-LIST

The National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology (NMEICT) was launched on 3rd Feb, 2009. It initiated a project called National Library and Information Services Infrastructure for Scholarly Content, popularly known as N-LIST which was formally launched by the Union Minister for Human Resource Development, on 4th May, 2010. The N-LIST Project is being jointly executed by the UGC-INFONET Digital Library Consortium, INFLIBNET Centre and the INDEST-AICTE Consortium, Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Delhi. The project provides the cross-subscription to e-

resources subscribed by the two Consortia, i.e. subscription to INDEST-AICTE resources for universities and UGC-INFONET resources for technical institutions; and the access to selected e-resources to colleges.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Akinola obtained the results from her study which revealed that majority of the respondents 35.4% from the university of Ibadan sought information to update knowledge¹. It was also found that the respondents also sought information for writing of papers or books, reading, and for preparing class lectures. The study on information seeking behaviour of Social Science faculty was done by Chattwal which indicates the pen-drive is most preferred as an external storage device due to its large storage capacity as well as convenience of usage was found to be the most preferred by 50.20% participants database appears to be the most suitable usage pattern for the University faculty members². The present study indicates that the main reason for not using N-LIST e-resources is 'lack of awareness' by student non-users respondents. A similar study by Nikam & Pramodini indicates that reasons of non-use of UGC-INFONET resources by the faculty members and research scholars was 59.50% of respondents attributed the

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reason as lack of training/ orientation³. The other reason included 28.50% of respondents attributed the reasons as 'lack of awareness' whereas 10.50% opted 'Aware but internet connection is not proper'. The authors concluded that the use was marginal and the scientist in the Mysore University Campus need constant guidance and training to maximise the use of UGC-INFONET e-resources. The similar study by Bhardwaj & Walia analyse the rating of the quality of the Electronic Resources in the St. Stephens College library, where majority of the respondents 52.8% agreed that the 'Quality of the N-LIST e-resources are excellent' while 39.68% of the respondents rated the quality of the N-LIST e-resources were good⁴. The authors also concluded that most of the respondents rated N-LIST e-resources very good. The similar study by Chikkanmanju & Kumbar identified the level of satisfaction of student respondents about the information retrieved through the N-LIST e-resources of the Tumkur University⁵. The study reveals that 46.86% opined that the aided college students are extremely satisfied with the information retrieved through the N-LIST e-resources.

OBJECTIVES

- To analyse the level of satisfaction amongst the faculty and students for the library assistance/ support provided by the member colleges.
- To analyse the level of satisfaction amongst the faculty and students for the ICT infrastructural facilities provided by the member colleges.

Hypothesis

- Hypotheses H₀ 1 (A) - The faculty are dissatisfied with the library support/ assistance provided by the member colleges.
- H₁ 1 (A) - The faculty are satisfied with the library support/ assistance provided by the member colleges.
- Hypotheses H₀ 1 (B) - The students are dissatisfied with the library support/ assistance provided by the member colleges.
- H₁ 1 (B) - The students are satisfied with the library support/ assistance provided by the member colleges.
- Hypotheses H₀ 2A - The faculty are dissatisfied with the ICT Infrastructural facilities provided by the member colleges.
- H₁ 2A - The faculty are satisfied with the ICT Infrastructural facilities provided by the member colleges.
- Hypotheses H₀ 2 B - The students are dissatisfied with the ICT Infrastructural facilities provided by the member colleges.
- H₁ 2 B - The students are satisfied with the ICT Infrastructural facilities provided by the member colleges.

METHODOLOGY AND SCOPE

A survey method has been implemented to meet the objectives of the study. The author has collected the data through questionnaire method from the selected degree colleges which are affiliated to Panjab University. The data have been collected from the 144 faculty users and 142 student users. The statistical ANOVA-test has been applied to approve the null or alternate hypothesis. This method facilitates yearly accumulation of information from the member colleges in various settings under parameters relevant to the study. This study is confined to 32 member colleges. These member colleges are located in Punjab and Chandigarh and are affiliated to Panjab University only.

DATA ANALYSIS

Demography

Demography refers to the fundamental and measurable statistics of a population with characteristics such as gender, age, education etc. to which the faculty and student users belong to. The table below will also provide demographic statistics of student users' respondents in terms of gender, age, education.

Table 1: Demography of Faculty & Student

Faculty (User)		N (%age)	Student (Users)		N (%age)
Gender	Male	30 (20.83)	Gender	Male	33 (23.24)
	Female	114 (79.17)		Female	109 (76.76)
Age	25-34	84 (58.33)	Age	18-21	80 (56.34)
	35-44	60 (41.67)		22-24	58 (40.85)
	Above 44	0 (0)		Above 24	4 (2.82)
Designation	Professor	3 (2.08)	Education	Pursuing Graduate	23 (16.20)
	Associate Professor	17 (11.81)		Pursuing Post graduate	119 (83.80)
	Assistant Professor	124 (86.11)			

Fig.1: Gender

Gender

The gender wise distribution of respondents is presented in the above figure. The responses have been received from male and female respondents from the colleges through a detailed investigation. It has been analysed that out of 144 faculty users, 79.17% respondents are females while 20.83% are males whereas in the student users there are total 142 respondents from which 76.76% are the females and 23.24% are males. The above data reveals that the representation of female respondents is much more than that of the male respondents in both the categories.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypotheses H₀ 1 A- The faculty are dissatisfied with the library support/ assistance provided by the member colleges.

H₁ 1 A - The faculty are satisfied with the library support/ assistance provided by the member colleges.

From combining the scores of satisfied and extremely satisfied, that the majority of the faculty respondents i.e. 82.64% were satisfied with the help of library staff while using N-LIST. But 79.86% of respondents are satisfied with the reference service provided by the library staff. Whereas only 77.09% of faculty respondents were satisfied with the training provided by library staff. However 70.14% and 78.47% of faculty respondents were also satisfied with the alerting services and article delivery services by the library staff.

Table 2A: Satisfaction level of Faculty towards Library Support

Sr. No.	Satisfaction/ Library Support	Extremely Satisfied	Moderately Satisfied	Satisfied	Somewhat Satisfied	Not Satisfied	Total
		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
1.	Help of Library Staff	50 (34.72%)	7 (4.86%)	69 (47.92%)	14 (9.72%)	4 (2.78%)	144 (100%)
2.	Training provided by the Library Staff	25 (17.36%)	15 (10.42%)	71 (49.31%)	25 (17.36%)	8 (5.56%)	144 (100%)
3.	Reference Service	43 (29.86%)	17 (11.81%)	55 (38.19%)	16 (11.11%)	13 (9.03%)	144 (100%)
4.	Alerting Service	25 (17.36%)	5 (3.47%)	71 (49.31%)	15 (10.42%)	28 (19.44%)	144 (100%)
5.	Article Delivery Services	28 (19.44%)	5 (3.47%)	80 (55.56%)	14 (9.72%)	17 (11.81%)	144 (100%)
Chi-Square d.f.		63.5 16		P-value	.000**		

From the scales of not satisfied and somewhat satisfied, also revealed that majority of respondents i.e. 21.53% are not satisfied with the article delivery services. Moreover, 17.36% are somewhat satisfied with the training provided by the library staff. The calculated Chi-square value and p-value are 63.5 and .000 shows the level of satisfaction for library support among the faculty respondents at 5% level of significance, hence we reject null hypothesis and accepts

the alternate hypothesis i.e. the faculty are satisfied with the library support facilities provided by the member colleges.

Hence, the findings reject the Null Hypothesis H_0 1A.

Hypotheses H_0 1 B- The student are dissatisfied with the library support/ assistance provided by the member colleges.

H_1 1 B - The students are satisfied with the library support/ assistance provided by the member colleges.

Table 2B: Satisfaction level of Students towards Library Support

Sr. No.	Satisfaction/ Library Support	Extremely satisfied	Moderately satisfied	Satisfied	Somewhat satisfied	Not Satisfied	Total
		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
1.	Help of Library Staff	44 (30.99%)	6 (4.23%)	70 (49.30%)	6 (4.23%)	16 (11.27%)	142 (100%)
2.	Training provided by the Library Staff	20 (14.08%)	8 (5.63%)	58 (40.85%)	30 (21.13%)	26 (18.31%)	142 (100%)
3.	Reference Service	30 (21.13%)	10 (7.04%)	48 (33.80%)	8 (5.63%)	46 (32.39%)	142 (100%)
4.	Alerting Service	20 (14.08%)	6 (4.23%)	54 (38.03%)	10 (7.04%)	52 (36.62%)	142 (100%)
5.	Article Delivery	26 (18.31%)	6 (4.23%)	56 (39.44%)	6 (4.23%)	48 (33.80%)	142 (100%)
Chi-Square d.f.		81.3 16		P-value			

The above table reveals the satisfaction level of student respondents by the library support while using N-LIST e-resources. From combining the scores of satisfied and fully satisfied, it was perceived that the majority of the student respondents i.e. 80.29% agree with the statement that they were satisfied with the help of library staff while using N-LIST e-resources. While only 54.93% of respondents were satisfied with the training provided by library staff. But 54.93% of respondents were satisfied with the 'reference service' provided by the library staff. However 52.11% and 57.75% of student respondents were also satisfied with the alerting services and article delivery services by the library staff.

From the scores of 'not satisfied' and 'somewhat satisfied', it has been revealed that 36.62% were also not satisfied with the article delivery service. Moreover, 21.13% were somewhat satisfied with the training provided by the library staff.

From combining the scales of 'satisfied', 'moderately satisfied' and 'extremely satisfied', the majority of student respondents i.e. 84.52% agree with the statement that the student respondents were satisfied with 'help of library staff' while using N-LIST e-resources. The calculated Chi-square value and p-value i.e. 81.3 and .000 show the level of satisfaction for library support among the student respondents at 5% level of significance, hence null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted i.e. the students are satisfied with the library support facilities provided by the

member colleges.

Hence, the findings reject the Null Hypothesis H_0 4B.

Hypotheses H_0 2A- The faculty are dissatisfied with the ICT Infrastructural facilities provided by the member colleges.

H_1 2A - The faculty are satisfied with the ICT Infrastructural facilities provided by the member colleges.

The above table understands the satisfaction level of the faculty respondents for ICT Infrastructure provided to them by the college administration in the various member colleges considered under the study.

From combining the scores of satisfied and fully satisfied it was perceived that majority 80.56% respondents were satisfied with the number of computer terminals installed in the colleges. While 68.75% of faculty respondents were satisfied with the internet accessibility and 68.75% were satisfied with the uninterrupted power supply. 65.28% of faculty respondents were satisfied with the application software. It was found that only 24.30% of faculty were satisfied with the Wi-Fi facility.

From the scores of 'not satisfied' and 'somewhat satisfied', it has been analysed that 21.53% of faculty respondents are not satisfied and 35.42% were somewhat satisfied with the 'Wi-Fi facility' provided by the various member colleges. Whereas 37.50% of participants were not satisfied and 13.89% were somewhat satisfied with the system hardware installed in the

Table 3: Faculty (ICT Infrastructure)

Sr. No.	Satisfaction/ ICT Support	Extremely satisfied	Moderately satisfied	Satisfied	Somewhat satisfied	Not satisfied	Total
		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
1.	Computer Terminals	35 (24.31%)	3 (2.08%)	81 (56.25%)	4 (2.78%)	21 (14.58%)	144 (100%)
2.	Internet accessibility	36 (25%)	26 (18.06%)	63 (43.75%)	11 (7.64%)	8 (5.56%)	144 (100%)
3.	Wi-Fi Facility	14 (9.72%)	27 (18.75%)	21 (14.58%)	51 (35.42%)	31 (21.53%)	144 (100%)
4.	Uninterrupted Power Supply	31 (21.53%)	25 (17.36%)	68 (47.22%)	20 (13.89%)	0 (0%)	144 (100%)
5.	Printing Facility	33 (22.92%)	21 (14.58%)	65 (45.14%)	13 (9.03%)	12 (8.33%)	144 (100%)
6.	System Hardware	21 (14.58%)	21 (14.58%)	68 (47.22%)	20 (13.89%)	14 (9.72%)	144 (100%)
7.	Application Software	33 (22.92%)	21 (14.58%)	61 (42.36%)	21 (14.58%)	8 (5.56%)	144 (100%)
Chi-Square d.f.		185 20		P-value		.000**	

computers which is available in the member colleges.

But the majority of the faculty respondents i.e. 80.56% are satisfied with the number of computer terminals installed in the colleges.

The calculated Chi-square value and p-value i.e. 185 and .000 show the level of satisfaction for ICT infrastructure by the faculty respondents at 5% level of significance, hence null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is

accepted i.e. the faculty respondents are satisfied with the ICT infrastructural facilities provided by the member colleges.

Hence, the findings reject the Null Hypothesis $H_0 2A$.

Hypotheses $H_0 2 B$ - The students are dissatisfied with the ICT Infrastructural facilities provided by the member colleges.

$H_1 2 B$ - The students are satisfied with the ICT Infrastructural facilities provided by the member colleges.

Table 4: (Student) ICT Infrastructure

Sr. No.	Satisfaction/ ICT Support	Extremely satisfied	Moderately satisfied	satisfied	Somewhat Satisfied	Not satisfied	Total
		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
1.	Computer Terminals	29 20.42%	4 2.82%	68 47.89%	18 12.68%	25 17.61%	142 (100%)
2.	Internet accessibility	33 23.24%	33 23.24%	48 33.80%	4 2.82%	26 18.31%	142 (100%)
3.	Wi-Fi Facility	15 10.56%	33 23.94%	19 13.38%	15 9.15%	62 43.66%	142 (100%)
4.	Uninterrupted Power Supply	25 17.61%	39 27.46%	48 33.80%	30 21.13%	0 0%	142 (100%)
5.	Printing Facility	27 19.01%	21 14.79%	58 40.85%	36 25.35%	28 19.72%	142 (100%)
6.	System Hardware	25 17.61%	21 14.79%	64 45.07%	16 11.27%	16 11.27%	142 (100%)
7.	Application Software	27 19.01%	17 11.97%	38 26.76%	34 23.94%	26 18.31%	142 (100%)
Chi-Square d.f.		204 24		P-value		.000**	

The above table understands the satisfaction level of the student respondents for ICT Infrastructure provided to them by the college administration in the various member colleges considered under the study.

From combining the scores of 'Satisfied'(S) and 'Fully Satisfied'(FS), the study reveals that 68.31% of student respondents were satisfied with the number of computer terminals installed in the colleges. While 57.04% of student respondents were satisfied with the internet accessibility, 51.41% and 62.68% of student respondents are satisfied with uninterrupted power supply and system hardware, respectively whereas 59.86% of students were satisfied with the printing facility. 45.77% of student respondents are satisfied with the application software. It was analysed that only 23.94% of student respondents are satisfied with the Wi-Fi facility in the college.

From the scores of 'not satisfied' and 'somewhat satisfied', it has been analysed that the majority of student respondents

i.e. 43.66% were not satisfied and 9.15% were somewhat satisfied with the 'Wi-Fi facility' provided by the various member colleges. Whereas 18.31% of participants were not satisfied and 23.94% were somewhat satisfied with the application software installed in the computers which is available in the member colleges.

Although the students were not satisfied with the Wi-Fi facility provided in their colleges, but as perceived above they were satisfied with the other infrastructural facilities provided to them except Wi-Fi facility. Therefore, the majority of the student respondents i.e. 68.31% were fully satisfied with the number of computer terminals installed in the colleges.

The calculated Chi-square value and p-value i.e. 204 and .000 show the significant level of satisfaction at 5% for ICT infrastructure by the student respondents, hence null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted i.e. the student respondents are satisfied with the ICT infrastructural facilities provided by the member colleges.

Hence, the findings reject the Null Hypothesis H_0 2B.

FINDINGS

- A majority of faculty and student respondents are satisfied with 'help of library staff' provided by the library staff.
- Both faculty and student respondent are not satisfied with the 'Article Delivery Services'. Moreover, they are somewhat satisfied with the training provided by the library staff.
- A majority of the faculty and students respondents are extremely satisfied with the number of computer terminals installed and with the ICT infrastructural facilities provided by the member colleges.
- It has been analysed that 21.53% of faculty respondents were not satisfied and 35.42% were somewhat satisfied with the 'Wi-Fi facility' provided by the various member colleges.
- 43.66% of student respondents were not satisfied with the 'Wi-Fi facility' provided by the various member colleges

SUGGESTIONS

The study at hand was focused on the evaluation of usage of N-LIST e-resources in the selected degree colleges affiliated to Panjab University, Chandigarh. The libraries should endeavour to launch a marketing plan to promote the usage of N-LIST e-resources and its awareness among the users through email alerts, text messages, social networking sites, WhatsApp groups, Blogs, and Wikis etc. It is suggested that the subscription cost of N-LIST e-resources should be reduced to the same as earlier for the non-aided colleges also.

Further the research in this regard will widen the criteria of the study and identify as to how the faculty and the student from the member colleges affiliated to other Universities explore the usage of the N-LIST e-resources. The authors feel that there is a need for appropriate and constant evaluation of this study in order to enhance insight into the usage analysis and the relevance of the information retrieved from the N-LIST e-resources.

REFERENCES

1. Akinola, S.F. (2009). Information seeking behaviour of lecturers in faculties of education in Obafemi Awolowo University, Heife and University of Ibadan. *Samaru Journal of Information Studies*, 9(2), 30.
2. Chattwal, A. (2014). Information seeking behaviour of Social Science faculty: A study of universities of Punjab, Haryana and Chandigarh. (*Unpublished Doctoral Thesis*). Panjab University, Chandigarh (India).
3. Nikam, K. & Pramodini, B. (2007). Use of e-Journals and databases by the academic community of university of Mysore: A survey. *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, 54(1), 19-22.
4. Bhardwaj, R. K. & Walia, P. K. (2012). Web based information sources and services: A case study of St. Stephen's College, University of Delhi. *Library Philosophy and Practice* .<http://www.webpages.uidaho.edu/~mbolin/K-walia.html>.
5. Chikkanmanju & Kumbar, M. (2015). Use of information resources and services by the students of first grade colleges affiliated to Tumkur University, Tumkur: A comparative study. *International Journal of Academic Library and Information Science*, 3(2), 53-64.
6. Kumbar, D., Chikkamanju & Kumar, G. K. (2013). Use of N-LIST e-resources by the faculty and student of university of Mysore constituent degree colleges: A comparative study. *National Seminar on Emerging Trends in ERMS in College Libraries*. ISBN: 978-93-83302-01-7, 6.
7. Krejice, R.V. & Morgan, D.W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurements*, 30, 607-610.
8. Proportionate Random Stratified Sampling (2013). In [Stattek.com](http://stattrek.com/statistics/resources.aspx). Retrieved on 18May, 2013.
9. Sethi, B. & Panda, K. C. (2012). Use of e-resources by life scientists: A case study of Sambalpur University, India. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. 681. Retrieved from <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/681>.